

Dibenzoanthradiquinone Building Blocks for the Synthesis of Nitrogenated Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons.

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ABSTRACT: A straightforward method for the synthesis of two dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-5,6,12,13-diquinone building blocks is reported. To showcase their usefulness, a series of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene nitrogenated derivatives have been synthesized that show different optoelectronic, redox and charge transport properties, illustrating their potential as organic semiconductors.

The synthesis of increasingly large polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)¹ is attracting growing attention due to their potential applications in electronics, photonics, energy storage and conversion, sensing and information storage, among others. PAHs can be considered small cut outs of graphene that show discrete HOMO-LUMO gaps and energy levels that can be tuned with the number of fused rings, their arrangement and the number and position of embedded heteroatoms, providing an infinite number of possibilities to prepare organic semiconductors with different properties.

Cyclocondensation reactions between *o*-quinone and *o*-diamine precursors have been widely used for the construction of nitrogen-doped PAHs (N-PAHs).^{1c-f} On one hand this type of condensation fuses together the π -systems of both precursors through the formation of a pyrazine ring, while on the other hand, it introduces simultaneously two electron-withdrawing nitrogen atoms in the framework. Our ability to increase structural complexity by using such cyclocondensation reactions depends on the development of efficient methods to synthesize PAHs with sets of *o*-quinones and *o*-diamines in different positions. To date there is a number *o*-quinones that have been used in the synthesis of complex N-PAHs, some of which include *o*-quinones of anthracene,² phenanthrene,³ phenanthroline,^{3b} pyrene,^{1f,4} coronene,⁵ hexabenzocoronene⁶ and graphene quantum dots.⁷ However, the methods for the introduction *o*-quinones in PAHs are not always straightforward or general. Not surprisingly, their use depends directly on their synthetic availability. For example, although, the synthesis of pyrene *o*-quinones was reported in 1937,^{4a} it was not until 2005^{4b} when they became accessible through a one-step method from pyrene derivatives, which resulted in a substantial increase in their interest.

Dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene (**1a**) is constituted by five fused rings and can be structurally described as a planarized tri-*p*-phenylene group fused to two additional rings in opposite bays (Figure 1). Electronically, this arrangement gives rise to two three Clar sextets, one on each ring of the tri-*p*-phenylene residue, and to two K-regions with a double bond character. The oxidation of the K-regions of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene to the di-*o*-quinone (**2a**) and its subsequent derivatization with *o*-phenylenediamine to produce the corresponding diquinoxaline have been described by Stephenson in 1949.⁸ However, dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-di-*o*-quinone **2a** was obtained as a by-product of the synthesis of the mono-*o*-quinone and its isolation was only partially achieved by fractional sublimation. Since then, to the best of our knowledge, there has been an additional report describing diquinone **2a**, but just as an undesired oxidation byproduct in 1958.⁹ Therefore, alternative methods need to be sought.

Herein, we make available a straightforward method for the synthesis of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-5,6,12,13-di-quinones **2a** and **2b** from their respective dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracenes **1a** and **1b**. In addition, we describe a synthetic methodology to prepare dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracenes **1a** and **1b** in a gram scale that does not involve any chromatographic purification. To showcase the usefulness of di-*o*-quinones **2a** and **2b** as building blocks, a series of N-PAHs (**3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**) have been synthesized by cyclocondensation with different *o*-diamines leading to a small library of derivatives that show different electronic absorption and fluorescence properties that cover the visible and the NIR, different redox properties, and pseudoconductivity values that illustrate their potential as organic semiconductors.

Figure 1. Dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracenes (**1a** and **1b**) and dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-di-o-quinones (**2a** and **2b**). Library of N-PAHs **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**.

The synthesis of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene (Scheme 1) started with the iodination of commercially available 1,4-dibromobenzene **6** into diiodide **7**. Next, (trimethylsilyl)ethynyl groups were introduced by Sonogashira coupling on the iodide positions to generate dibromide **8**, which was subsequently subjected to Suzuki coupling with phenylboronic acid to yield **9a**. Desilylation of **9a** into **10a** took place quantitatively. Benzannulation of **10a** using PtCl_2 yielded dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene **1a** in a 57%. All these synthetic steps required no chromatographic purification and therefore **1a** could be prepared straightforward. Chemoselective oxidation of the K-regions was first attempted using NaIO_4 and RuCl_3 but only small amounts of the desired diquinone **2b** (> 1%) were obtained after chromatographic purification. Longer reaction times or reoxidation of the crude under the same conditions did not alter the outcome of this reaction. Notably, after work-up a large amount of a dark reddish crude mixture was obtained, which we suspected it was a mixture of different oxidation intermediates of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene diquinone. When we subjected this crude mixture to a subsequent oxidation process using $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, the yields after chromatography improved substantially to 14%. Diquinone **2a** showed a very limited solubility and could only be characterized by IR. Diquinone **2a** was then allowed to react with *o*-phenylenediamine **11**¹⁰ in a 3:1 mixture of CHCl_3 :AcOH yielding **3a** in 59% as a yellow solid (Scheme 2). It was found that **3a** was scarcely soluble in common organic solvents such as CHCl_3 or toluene, but still thanks to the four tri-*iso*-propylsilyl (TIPS) groups, it was possible to establish its structure by NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) and MS, which confirmed not only the structure of **3a** but also that of diquinone **2a**.

Given the low solubility of **2a** and **3a**, we decided to introduce *tert*-butyl groups in positions 3 and 10 of the dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene core. To do so, a *tert*-butyl substituted phenylboronic acid was employed in the Suzuki reaction step that generated **9b** (87%) with two *tert*-butyl groups in the tri-*p*-phenylene core. Following then, the same synthetic route used for **2a**. Tri-

p-phenylene **9b** was subjected to desilylation into **10b** (>99%) and subsequently to PtCl_2 catalyzed benzannulation (63%) to provide 3,10-di-*tert*-butyl-dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene **1b** in a gram scale without any chromatographic purification. Then oxidation of **1b** using $\text{NaIO}_4/\text{RuCl}_3$ and subsequently $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, yielded the desired 3,10-di-*tert*-butyldibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-5,6,12,13-diquinone **2b** (17%) was obtained. Diquinone **2b** was highly soluble in comparison to **2a** and it could be characterized by NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) and HRMS.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for the preparation of the dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-5,6,12,13-diquinones.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of N-PAHs **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** by condensation of dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene-5,6,12,13-diquinones **2a** and **2b** with the corresponding *o*-diamines **11**, **12** and **13**.

At this stage, we assessed the reactivity of diquinone **2b** with different diamines with an increasingly long aromatic core. Diquinone **1b** was allowed to react with 1,2-phenylenediamine **11**, 5,6-diaminobenzothiadiazole **12**¹¹ and 2,3-diaminophenazine **13**¹² in a 3:1 mixture of CHCl_3 :AcOH (Scheme 2). *N*-doped PAHs **3a** (76%), **4** (22%) and **5** (37%) were isolated, respectively, by flash chromatography as yellow, dark red and purple solids, respectively, and were highly soluble in halogenated or aromatic solvents at room temperature, which allowed their characterization by NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) and HRMS.

Needle shaped crystals suitable for X-Ray diffraction were obtained for **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**, which further confirmed their structure (Figure 2). The X-ray structures show that the aromatic cores are virtually flat in all cases but in the case of **3b**, in

which one of the quinoxaline arms is out-of-plane. Conversely, the packing is quite different. In the case of **3a** the molecules are π - π stacked (3.49 Å), while in the case of **3b** with the *tert*-butyl group the packing is herringbone. The crystal structure of compound **4** combined π - π (3.55 Å) and herringbone stacking. The structure of **5** showed a clear π - π stacking (3.41 Å) between molecules. The nuclear independent chemical shift (NICS) values calculated for **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** (Figure S1). The NICS(0) values of the *tri-p*-phenylene residue of the dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene core oscillate between -3.9 and -6.0 ppm, while NICS(0) values of the K-region rings oscillate between +2.9 and +5.1 ppm, which is consistent with the aromatic and antiaromatic character, respectively, predicted by Clar rules. The NICS(0) values of the additional rings oscillate between -3.4 and -14.9 ppm, which is consistent with the quinoxaline, diazanaphthothiadiazole and tetraazatetracene character of **3**, **4** and **5**, respectively.

Figure 2. Front view (left) and packing (right) of (a) **3a**, (b) **3b**, (c) **4** and (d) **5** observed on the crystal structures.

Solutions of **3**, **4** and **5** show the same bright colors as the corresponding solids. Compounds **3a** and **3b** show a similar bright yellow color, while the solutions of **4** and **5** are red and dark red, respectively (Figure S2). The UV-vis absorption of **3a** and **3b** (Figure 3a and Table S1) show similar absorption features with a small bathochromic for **3b** of the band around 450 nm. The absorption spectra of **4** and **5** show the same set of bands observed for **3a** and **3b**, but bathochromically shifted. The shifts increase with number of rings fused to the dibenzoanthracene core. TD-DFT calculations carried out at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level showed the same trend in the absorption maxima (Figure S3 and Table S2). The lowest energy band corresponds in all cases to the HOMO-LUMO transition. The optical HOMO-LUMO gaps were estimated from the onset of the longest wavelength absorption (2.63, 2.49, 1.94 and 1.82 eV, respectively for **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**) and show the same trends as the calculated ones (Table S2).

The solutions of **3** and **4** under UV light show a green and red fluorescence, while no fluorescence could be observed for **5** with the naked eye (Figure S2). The fluorescence spectra of **3b** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 502$ nm; $\Phi = 0.09$) appears bathochromically shifted in comparison to **3a** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 470$ nm; $\Phi = 0.08$), in agreement with the electronic absorption spectra (Figure 3b and Table S1). The fluorescence spectra of **4** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 632$ nm; $\Phi = 0.36$) and **5** ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 670$ nm; $\Phi = 0.10$) extend between the red and the NIR regions.

Figure 3. a) Molar absorptivity coefficients in CHCl₃; b) normalized fluorescence spectra and quantum yields in CHCl₃; c) CV curves in 0.1 M solution of *n*Bu₄NPF₆ in CH₂Cl₂. Potentials versus Fc/Fc⁺; and d) FP-TRMC ($\lambda=355$ nm, $I_0=9.1 \times 10^{15}$ photons cm⁻²) of products **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**.

The cyclic voltammograms of **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** were recorded in CH₂Cl₂ using *n*Bu₄NPF₆ as electrolyte and ferrocene (Fc/Fc⁺) as reference (Figure 3c). In products **3a**, **3b** and **4** two different reduction processes were observed. In the case of **3a** a small cathodic current at low potentials was attributed to aggregation as noted for similar compounds.¹³ The redox potentials (Table S3) were similar for **3a** and **3b** (-1.52 and -1.72 V; -1.54 and -1.71 V, respectively) and, while they were less cathodic than **4** (-0.93 and -1.04 V). The voltammograms of **5** showed the same set of two reduction processes but at even lower cathodic potentials and with an additional reduction wave (-0.69, -0.81 and -1.23 V). None of these products shows any redox process in the oxidative scan. The electrochemical LUMO levels (or electron affinities) were estimated from the onset of the first reduction are -3.59, -3.60, -3.92 and -4.17 eV for **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** respectively (Table S4). These values are in a reasonable agreement with the ones calculated at the B3LYP-CH₂Cl₂-6-311+g(2d,p)/B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level of theory (Table S5).

The charge transporting properties of **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** were evaluated by flash-photolysis time-resolved microwave conductivity (FP-TRMC)¹⁴ directly on the powder solids (Figures 3d and S4). This contactless technique allows measuring directly the pseudoconductivity ($\phi \Sigma \mu_{\text{max}}$) that can be considered

the minimum/intrinsic mobility of the material. $\phi\Sigma\mu_{\max}$ values approaching $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ were obtained in all cases. Compounds **3a** and **3b** (0.69×10^{-4} and $0.65 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively) showed similar $\phi\Sigma\mu_{\max}$ values, which were slightly lower for **4** and **5** (0.54×10^{-4} and $0.44 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively). These values are in the same range as those observed on molecular organic semiconductors.¹⁴⁻¹⁵

The frontier orbitals calculated at the B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) show that the electron densities in both the HOMO and the LUMO spread throughout the whole aromatic core, indicating that these are highly conjugated systems (Figure 4). In the case of the HOMO, the densities over the external rings of the tri-*p*-phenylene residue decrease as the number of rings increase along the K-regions. While in the case of the LUMOs, the electron densities are mostly localized over the extended K-regions and appear to be conjugated through the central ring of the tri-*p*-phenylene residue.

Figure 4. Frontier orbitals at the B3LYP-6-31g(d,p) level for **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**.

In summary, we have reported a methodology to prepare and isolate two inaccessible and valuable building blocks for the synthesis of N-PAHs, namely dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene di-*o*-quinones **2a** and **2b**, including a gram scale synthesis of the corresponding dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene precursors that does not involve any chromatographic purification. To showcase, the usefulness of di-*o*-quinones **2a** and **2b** as building blocks, a series of N-PAHs (**3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5**) have been synthesized by cyclocondensation with different *o*-diamines leading to a small library of derivatives. Optoelectronic, redox and theoretical studies on **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** confirm that dibenzo[*a,h*]anthracene di-*o*-quinones are a highly tunable platform to prepare N-PAHs with a broad range of absorbing and emitting properties that extend from the visible into the NIR, which combined with their low LUMO levels and $\phi\Sigma\mu_{\max}$ values approaching $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, illustrate their potential as organic semiconductors. Overall this work makes accessible a family of derivatives that have received virtually no attention since 1949, expanding the building block toolbox for the synthesis of N-PAHs.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Figures S1-S4, Table S1-S5, general methods and full synthesis and characterization details of **3a**, **3b**, **4** and **5** can be found in the ESI. (PDF)

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors.

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REFERENCES

- (a) Akasaka, T.; Osuka, A.; Fukuzumi, S.; Kandori, H., *Chemical Science of π -Electron Systems*. Springer: Tokyo, 2015; (b) Miao, Q., *Polycyclic Arenes and Heteroarenes: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications*. Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA: 2015; (c) Bunz, U. H. F.; Freudenberg, J., "N-Heteroarenes and N-Heteroarenes as N-Nanocarbon Segments", *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52*, 1575-1587; (d) Mateo-Alonso, A., "Synthetic Approaches to Pyrene-Fused Twistacenes", *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2017**, *2017*, 7006-7011; (e) Stępień, M.; Gońka, E.; Żyła, M.; Sprutta, N., "Heterocyclic Nanographenes and Other Polycyclic Heteroaromatic Compounds: Synthetic Routes, Properties, and Applications", *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 3479-3716; (f) Mateo-Alonso, A., "Pyrene-fused pyrazaacenes: from small molecules to nanoribbons", *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 6311-6324.
- (a) Richter, M.; Hahn, S.; Dmitrieva, E.; Rominger, F.; Popov, A.; Bunz, U. H. F.; Feng, X.; Berger, R., "Helical Ullazine-Quinoxaline-Based Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons", *Chem. Eur. J.* **2019**, *25*, 1345-1352; (b) Hahn, S.; Koser, S.; Hodecker, M.; Tverskoy, O.; Rominger, F.; Dreuw, A.; Bunz, U. H. F., "Alkyne-Substituted N-Heterophenes", *Chem. Eur. J.* **2017**, *23*, 8148-8151.
- (a) Lindner, B. D.; Zhang, Y.; Höfle, S.; Berger, N.; Teusch, C.; Jesper, M.; Hardcastle, K. I.; Qian, X.; Lemmer, U.; Colsmann, A.; Bunz, U. H. F.; Hamburger, M., "N-Fused quinoxalines and benzoquinoxalines as attractive emitters for organic light emitting diodes", *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2013**, *1*, 5718-5724; (b) Li, G.; Wu, Y.; Gao, J.; Li, J.; Zhao, Y.; Zhang, Q., "Synthesis, Physical Properties, and Anion Recognition of Two Novel Larger Azaacenes: Benzannulated Hexazaheptacene and Benzannulated N,N'-Dihydrohexazaheptacene", *Chem. Asian J.* **2013**, *8*, 1574-1578; (c) Mahjoub, A. R.; Ghammami, S.; Kassae, M. Z., "Tetramethylammonium fluorochromate(VI): a new and efficient oxidant for organic substrates", *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2003**, *44*, 4555-4557; (d) Ghammami, S.; Eimanieh, H.; Mohammady, M. K., "Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromochromate: A New and Efficient Oxidant for Organic Substrates", *Synth. Commun.* **2007**, *37*, 599-605.
- (a) Vollmann, H.; Becker, H.; Corell, M.; Streeck, H., "Beiträge zur Kenntnis des Pyrens und seiner Derivate", *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.* **1937**, *531*, 1-159; (b) Hu, J.; Zhang, D.; Harris, F. W., "Ruthenium(III) chloride catalyzed oxidation of pyrene and 2,7-disubstituted pyrenes: An efficient, one-step synthesis of pyrene-4,5-diones and pyrene-4,5,9,10-tetraones", *J. Org. Chem.* **2005**, *70*, 707-708.
- (a) Rieger, R.; Kastler, M.; Enkelmann, V.; Müllen, K., "Entry to Coronene Chemistry—Making Large Electron Donors and Acceptors", *Chem. Eur. J.* **2008**, *14*, 6322-6325; (b) Jia, H.-P.; Liu, S.-X.; Sanguinet, L.; Levillain, E.; Decurtins, S., "Star-Shaped

- Tetrathiafulvalene-Fused Coronene with Large π -Extended Conjugation", *J. Org. Chem.* **2009**, *74*, 5727-5729.
6. (a) Fogel, Y.; Kastler, M.; Wang, Z.; Andrienko, D.; Bodwell, G. J.; Müllen, K., "Electron-Deficient N-Heteroaromatic Linkers for the Elaboration of Large, Soluble Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Their Use in the Synthesis of Some Very Large Transition Metal Complexes", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2007**, *129*, 11743-11749; (b) Jia, H.-P.; Ding, J.; Ran, Y.-F.; Liu, S.-X.; Blum, C.; Petkova, I.; Hauser, A.; Decurtins, S., "Targeting π -Conjugated Multiple Donor-Acceptor Motifs Exemplified by Tetrathiafulvalene-Linked Quinoxalines and Tetrabenz[bc,ef,hi,uv]ovalenes: Synthesis, Spectroscopic, Electrochemical, and Theoretical Characterization", *Chem. Asian J.* **2011**, *6*, 3312-3321; (c) Qiao, X.; Li, Q.; Schaugaard, R. N.; Noffke, B. W.; Liu, Y.; Li, D.; Liu, L.; Raghavachari, K.; Li, L.-s., "Well-Defined Nanographene-Rhenium Complex as an Efficient Electrocatalyst and Photocatalyst for Selective CO₂ Reduction", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2017**, *139*, 3934-3937.
 7. Li, Q.; Zhang, S.; Dai, L.; Li, L.-s., "Nitrogen-Doped Colloidal Graphene Quantum Dots and Their Size-Dependent Electrocatalytic Activity for the Oxygen Reduction Reaction", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 18932-18935.
 8. Stephenson, E. F. M., "551. The Schmidt reaction on 1 : 2-5 : 6-dibenzanthra-3 : 4-quinone", *J. Chem. Soc.* **1949**, 2620-2623.
 9. LaBudde, J. A.; Heidelberger, C., "The Synthesis of the Mono- and Dihydroxy Derivatives of 1,2,5,6-Dibenzanthracene Excreted by the Rabbit and of Other Hydroxylated Dibenzanthracene Derivatives¹", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1958**, *80*, 1225-1236.
 10. Lindner, B. D.; Engelhart, J. U.; Märken, M.; Tverskoy, O.; Appleton, A. L.; Rominger, F.; Hardcastle, K. I.; Enders, M.; Bunz, U. H. F., "Synthesis and Optical Properties of Diaza- and Tetraazatetracenes", *Chem. Eur. J.* **2012**, *18*, 4627-4633.
 11. Marco, A. B.; Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Gozalvez, C.; Olano, M.; Atxabal, A.; Sun, X.; Melle-Franco, M.; Hueso, L. E.; Mateo-Alonso, A., "An electron-conducting pyrene-fused phenazinotiadiazole", *Chem. Commun.* **2015**, *51*, 10754-10757.
 12. Lindner, B. D.; Engelhart, J. U.; Tverskoy, O.; Appleton, A. L.; Rominger, F.; Peters, A.; Himmel, H.-J.; Bunz, U. H. F., "Stable Hexacenes through Nitrogen Substitution", *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2011**, *50*, 8588-8591.
 13. More, S.; Bhosale, R.; Mateo-Alonso, A., "Low-LUMO Pyrene-Fused Azaacenes", *Chem. Eur. J.* **2014**, *20*, 10626-10631.
 14. Saeki, A.; Koizumi, Y.; Aida, T.; Seki, S., "Comprehensive Approach to Intrinsic Charge Carrier Mobility in Conjugated Organic Molecules, Macromolecules, and Supramolecular Architectures", *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2012**, *45*, 1193-1202.
 15. (a) Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Mora-Fuentes, J. P.; Strutyński, K.; Saeki, A.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., "Monodisperse N-Doped Graphene Nanoribbons Reaching 7.7 Nanometers in Length", *Angew. Chem.* **2018**, *130*, 711-716; (b) Mora-Fuentes, J. P.; Riaño, A.; Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Saeki, A.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., "Giant Star-Shaped Nitrogen-Doped Nanographenes", *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 552-556; (c) Cortizo-Lacalle, D.; Gozalvez, C.; Melle-Franco, M.; Mateo-Alonso, A., "A thiadiazole-capped nanoribbon with 18 linearly fused rings", *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 11297-11301.